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Pedagogical Orientation of Student Teachers to Universal Values

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Abstract

Relevance of the problem of pedagogical orientation of student teachers to universal values in the context of pedagogical education' transformation is determined by the globalization challenge. Globalization challenges cardinally change the whole education system, firstly, goals, values, meanings and results of education, secondly, models of teacher training, thirdly, models of educational practices, fourthly, poly-paradigm educational space's development strategy.

The goal of the article is to show the important role of pedagogical orientation of student teachers to universal values, especially in the context of globalization challenges to search for universal values' matrix and in pursuit of interiorization of universal values that can promote spiritual convergence and the integration of societies.

The problem of the student teachers' pedagogical orientation to universal values is considered using the methods, first of all, the method of constructive - genetic research of educational values, idealization and extrapolation.

The results of the study are the clarification of the term "an open system of universal values", development of universal values' matrix on the base of extrapolation, idealization and constructive - genetic research methods and a systematization of pedagogical conditions of students' orientation to universal values, which are adequate to a professional activities of future teachers.

Practical importance of research results is determined by the possibility of using theoretical positions and conclusion for their further realization in the process of pedagogical orientation of students to universal values. Recommendations for teachers on issues of students' orientation to universal values are offered. A special questionnaire and a method of assessment and self-assessment of students' level of universal values can be applied in the pedagogical practice.

Key words: pedagogical orientation of student teachers, universal values, universal values' matrix, an open system of universal values, axiologization of poly-paradigm educational environment at university.

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Introduction

The problem of pedagogical orientation of student teachers to universal values in conditions of pedagogical education' transformation is relevant and determined by the globalization challenge. Globalization challenges cardinally change the whole education system, firstly, goals, values, meanings and results of education, secondly, models of teacher training, thirdly, models of educational practices, fourthly, poly-paradigm educational space's development strategy.

One of the leading tendencies of the improvement of higher pedagogical education is a realization of values paradigm. The last decade is characterized by active orientation to the problem of values in education. In soviet period an obvious fact, according to Gershunsky (2003), was underestimated, the fact was «it is education as the most technologically advanced and the movable part of the culture, keeps its finger on the pulse of human values and ideals, individual and social mentality and world-view, behavioural priorities and specific actions». Therefore, a professional training of teachers should contribute to the formation of the mentality of the individual as the highest goal and value of education.

Axiological aspects of a future teacher training in the context of pedagogical university were considered in the works by Isaev (2004), Kiryakova (1996), Valeeva (2014), Nikandrov (2008), Slastenin & Chizhakova (2003), Andreev (2015), Shiyarov (1991).

The problem of values orientation was stated in the works by Ravkin (1995a), Boguslavsky (1996), Ravkin & Pryanikova (1996), Klarin (1998), Kraevsky (2006) and other researchers. Krayevsky's position (2006) is relevant in this context; the position is about necessity to strength the axiological aspects of psychological and pedagogical disciplines because axiology is a doctrine about values. Therefore, axiology is increasingly becoming a part of philosophical, social and pedagogical concepts.

In this way, the priority areas of research were axiological strategies of development of not only education, but also the economic and spiritual life of Russian society (Ravkin, 1995a). Probably, therefore, in the article "Development of education in Russia: new value orientations (research concept)" (Ravkin, 1995a), attention was focused on the axiological orientation which forms the base of strategy in educational sphere, in concept of which national and human values of spiritual society life are contained. (Ravkin, 1995b) claimed that «axiological orientations are historical, always belong to a particular era, have the ability to acquire a new meaning at a new turn of the historical movement. To come into contact with the values of the subsequent period, while maintaining a constructive-positive, enduring value», paying attention of contemporaries that in the distant future society, the sphere of education will be oriented on spiritual values which always acted as an ideal.

Purpose and objectives of the research

The goal of the article is to show important role of pedagogical orientation of student teachers to universal values, especially in the context of globalization educational challenge of searching for universal values' matrix as well as in pursuit of interiorization of universal values that can promote spiritual convergence and integration of societies.

Our researches show that it is necessary, firstly, to clarify the content of the concept of an open system of universal values, secondly, to develop universal values' matrix on the base of extrapolation, idealization and constructive - genetic research methods, thirdly, to systematize the pedagogical conditions of students' orientation to the universal values sufficient for professional activity of future teachers, fourthly, to consider mechanisms of assignment of universal values among people.

Literature review

Accepting the deep difference between different people His Holiness the 14th Dalai Lama constantly reminds us about the most important thing that unites people. Indeed, whether we are educated or not, regardless of our race, gender, religion, we all want to be happy and free from emotional and spiritual suffering. High levels of anxiety, dissatisfaction, nervous disorders, self-doubt, loneliness, depression are occurred in the world. After the careful thought, His Holiness the 14th Dalai Lama (2006) convinces us that all these problems are ethics and offers to make a spiritual revolution by developing a universal system of values not taking into account political, economic and technical revolutions.

In that way, before the pedagogical theory and innovative educational practice there are questions: what should be the value content of pedagogical education; what are the pedagogical legal documents and mechanisms of individual assigning of universal values; what is the base for classifying the open universal system of values.

Anyway, one of the important contradictions of pedagogical orientation of students (teachers) to universal values is a gap between a teacher who is assigned to a responsible mission as the bearer of universal values and meanings for the upbringing, education, development of the younger generation and the lack of axiologization of poly-paradigm educational space.

In this regard, according to the taught psychological and pedagogical modules it is necessary to highlight the axiological approach as a methodological base. In the opinion of researchers (Andreev, 2003; Isaev, 2004; Bondarevskaya, 1997; Slastenin & Chizhakova, 2003) the axiological approach gives the process of future teachers' training the humanistic direction. What is the most effective way to realize the axiological approach in poly-paradigm educational space of the university?

The most important problem of the axiological approach, as the interdisciplinary one, is the problem of valuable basis of human activity. Values are system-forming components of pedagogical activity; values regulate and direct activity, communication and interaction of the teacher with pupils.

What are values? Etymologically, the meaning of the word "value" corresponds to the term itself: value is what people value. «Values - according to Anisimov (1988) - are reflected in the minds of people in the form of value judgments and assessments».

As the researches show (Slastenin and Chizhakova, 2003), the concept of "value" in genesis indicates that it combines three main meanings:

- the definition of real-subject properties of phenomena, which is based on a practical and emotional ability of man to appreciate objects and phenomena;
- the definition of moral categories including the psychological characteristics of a person;
- the definition of social phenomena that characterize relationships between people.

Values also represent, according to Frankl (1990), «semantic universals crystallized as a result of generalization of typical situations which mankind had to face in history». From the Frankl's point of view (1990), meaning is not subjective because man does not invent it but finds it in the world and in the surrounding reality. Frankl suggests ways in which man can make his/her life meaningful:

- through what we give to life (in the sense of our creative work);
- through what we take from life (in the sense of experiencing values);
- through the position we take in relation to destiny, which we are unable to change.

Accordingly, there are three groups of values: creativity, experience and relationships. In pedagogical education there are typical situations in which the universal meanings becoming for the participants of the process of education value-personal are crystallized.

The researcher (Kiryakova, 1996) reviewed the orientation process as the ascent of the individual to values on the basis of the universal dialectical elevation of needs. Each person has an individual specific hierarchy of personal values, which serve as a link between the spiritual culture of society and the spiritual world of the individual. It should be noted that the evolution of the values of society is constantly changing priorities and hierarchy, devaluing some and putting forward others. Pedagogical orientation of student teachers to universal values can be defined as the formation of universal needs of student teachers, and it is necessary to pay attention to spiritual needs.

Methodology

In this research on the student teachers pedagogical orientation to universal values the following methods were used. First of all, the method of constructive - genetic research of educational values, idealization and extrapolation, observation, comparison and interpretation of factors and conditions of pedagogical orientation of students teachers to universal values in various situations of educational, prosocial, educational and professional activity.

In this regard, as the results of our study show, the purpose of the study is, firstly, to clarify the concept of an open system of universal values, secondly, to develop a matrix of universal values, based on the methods of extrapolation, idealization and method of constructive-genetic research of the education values; thirdly, the systematization of pedagogical conditions of orientation of students to universal values sufficient to professional activities of future teachers, and fourthly, consideration of the mechanism of assigning of universal values.

Experimental work was carried out on the base of Bashkir State University and Kazan (Volga region) Federal University. On the first step constructive-genetic analysis of educational values on the research problem was carried out, the research problem, goals, hypothesis was formulated. On the second step the matrix of universal values was developed, basic conditions for student teachers orientation to universal values were identified. On the third step research results were generalized, were developed methodical recommendations on the implementation of the research

results in the practice of teaching students at the university.

Results

Based on the analysis of philosophical, psychological and pedagogical literature, in the frame of our research the values that can be called universal values are distinguished:

- mental, vital values of the person and humanity in the context of different countries and nations;
- spiritual values as a set of moral, religious, ethical beliefs that represent the importance for a person;
- pedagogical, prevailing historically values in the development of society, educational system, and science (Evsetsova, 2008).

Particularly, it should be pointed that the spiritual, human, educational and mental values are interconnected and are interconnected in a hierarchical (interacting) ways. Human and pedagogical values are basic for the formation of mental values. As it already known, actions and human behaviour are driven by mentality, which, historically, is derived from the culture of the people, their religion, way of life, and education. Therefore, mental values have increased stability and inertia in comparison with human and pedagogical values. You should realize that as changes take place in conditions of socio-pedagogical reality, the elevation of the needs of the individual, society change and pedagogical values are measured.

The integral pedagogical process is a product of integration of spiritual, mental, human and pedagogical values.

Matrix of universal values

Mental values		Pedagogical values
	Universal values	
Spiritual values		Human values

During the process of professional training which consists of pedagogical and prosocial activities the teacher masters the pedagogical values and makes them subjective. The level of pedagogical values' subjectivation is a degree of realization of ideal-valuable transformation of potential. Every value is characterized by two peculiarities - functional meaning and individual sense. The individual sense of the value, on the one hand, determines by object performing the function of value, but on the other hand, depends on the person

During the process of student teachers' pedagogical orientation to universal values self-knowledge and self-esteem are produced. A human personality is created by value orientations, which are formed in his/her life experience and which he/she projects for the future. Further, the process acquires qualitatively new characteristics: reevaluation of values and building a hierarchal scale of values. In a system of universal values, the idea of free value self-determination of the individual based on the humanistic worldview is a priority. Therefore, the process of professional and pedagogical training should be focused on an system of universal values, focusing on the axiological aspects of the content of pedagogical orientation, the purposeful development of pedagogical ideals, norms of ethical pedagogical behaviour, principles and objectives of pedagogical activity, subjective values underlying the individual sense of universal values that determine the tactics and strategy of pedagogical activity. Open system of universal values is can be seen as the directly experienced by student teachers form of their attitude to the pedagogical reality, humanistic

personality-significant position in the process of professional pedagogical education, upbringing and creative self-development.

Education, thanks to its mass character and consistency, transforms universal values into the sphere of the emerging new consciousness and influences the processes taking place in spiritual life, economics and politics.

Discussions

Coexistence of poly-paradigm educational sphere, as it already known, not only does not destroy the integrity of pedagogical reality, but through the increasing of diversity contributes to its development. Despite the anthropological unity of humanity many modifications of pedagogical paradigms are being justified. Therefore, the question about universal pedagogical paradigm may be removed before the next scientific revolution in the minds of teachers-scientists and teachers-practitioners. As a result, the following questions should be answered:

- What is an invariant basis for poly-paradigm educational space?
- How do the pedagogical paradigms interact?

Invariant basis, as it shown in authors' researches, can be the universal values which organise pedagogical paradigms in integrity and strength it integration.

A generalized program of educational activities and the universal values of the integrity paradigm are encoded in every pedagogical paradigm. Universal values reflects the eternal problems of the teacher's existence, each paradigm solves them in its own way, only the meanings of universal values change.

Conclusion

Relevance of the problem of pedagogical orientation of student teachers to universal values in conditions of pedagogical education transformation is determined by the globalization challenge. Globalization challenges cardinally change the whole education system, firstly, goals, values, meanings and results of education, secondly, models of teacher training, thirdly, models of educational practices, fourthly, poly-paradigm educational space's development strategy.

The goal of the article is to show important role of pedagogical orientation of student teachers to universal values, especially in the context of globalization challenges to search for universal values' matrix and in pursuit of interiorization of universal values that can promote spiritual convergence and the integration of societies.

The problem of the student teachers' pedagogical orientation to universal values is considered using the methods, first of all, the method of constructive - genetic research of educational values, idealization and extrapolation.

The results of the study are clarified the concept of an open system of universal values and developed a matrix of universal values, based on the methods of extrapolation, idealization and the method of constructive genetic research of the values of education. Also, pedagogical conditions of orientation of students to universal values were systematized and adequate professional activity of future teachers was clarified.

The practical significance of the research results is determined by the possibility of using theoretical positions and conclusions for their realization in the process of pedagogical orientation of students to universal values. Recommendations for teachers on methods of orientation of students to universal values are offered. Special questionnaires and methods of assessment and self-assessment of the levels of universal values of students, which can be applied in the real pedagogical process, have been created.

The open system of universal values is understood as directly experienced by student teachers form of their attitude to the pedagogical reality, humanistic personality-significant position in the process of professional pedagogical education, upbringing and creative self-development.

Education, thanks to its mass character and consistency, transforms universal values into the sphere of the emerging new consciousness and influences the processes taking place in spiritual life, economics and politics.

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